

Emotion, Arousal, Attention and *Flow*

Chaining Emotional States to Improve Human-Computer Interaction

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Abstract

Current models utilized in designing to elicit emotional states describe how emotions are processed and how they are elicited. In order to describe how emotional states can be connected or *chained* to elicit behaviours that are beneficial to the user, several practical questions must also be addressed:

1. How can we tell emotions apart?
2. What emotional states should we be trying to elicit with design?
3. What characteristics of products must be addressed to affect people's emotions?
4. In what sequence should we elicit emotions?

These questions can be addressed by synthesizing existing research on emotional design with related research on appearance, interaction, behaviour, and state chaining. Emotions play a key role in determining the focus and intensity of our attention by affecting how we appraise situations and persuading us to voluntarily change some aspect of our attitudes, goals and behaviour. Emotional states affect how we learn, process and use information. Understanding emotional affect allows us to think about how emotional states are related and connected or *chained* to one another. This understanding can assist designers in creating interfaces that help both novice and experienced users overcome discouraging situations and find more satisfaction in the use of the software and electronic devices.

To aid in the visualization of emotional state chains, a "map" of the emotional landscape based on the affect circumplex can be used to understand how emotions are related, and to visualize chains of emotions that are beneficial to the user. Transferring the notion of "flow", or "optimal experience" to the affect circumplex gives the designer direction as to what states to elicit, and in what sequence to elicit them.

The relationship of the affect circumplex to appearance, interaction, personality and behaviour provides general guidelines for eliciting shifts in the dimensions of emotion (i.e., value and arousal). This allows the designer to understand which visual and interactive properties elicit emotional states, and how they can be connected or chained to help the user recover from negative situations.

Keywords

state chaining, interface design, interaction design, attention, flow, value, arousal, emotional state, emotional affect, persuasion, mobile,

Introduction

Today's mobile electronic devices and software are often so complex and confusing to operate that few people are able to fully utilize them. This means that mobile technology is often not implemented to its full potential. Problems using these technologies can often lead to errors, inefficiency and human frustration. This represents missed opportunities for innovation, poor returns on technology investments and failures to recognize and capitalize on human strengths. Our failure to tailor devices to human strengths while compensating for human weaknesses can lead to accidents which result in plane crashes, nuclear meltdowns, litigation and loss of life. (Vicente 2003)

The designer has many things to consider when creating complex interactions for mobile consumer products and systems. Adding the consideration of emotion to this equation can help to ensure satisfying product experiences for users. Considering emotion becomes even more important when designing systems for use in demanding, safety-sensitive environments where high levels of anxiety or "arousal" are commonplace. Designing for emotion doesn't replace existing techniques like usability assessments, information design, information architecture or interaction design. It also doesn't override existing priorities such as functionality, usability or aesthetics. An understanding of the factors that affect emotional elicitation ties these existing techniques and priorities together, allowing the designer to use them in a concerted way that benefits the user.

Even though we're responding to them all the time, we tend to notice our emotions only when they get intense enough to demand our attention. When that happens, it's because our level of anxiety or "arousal", increases. Many of our decisions are made because of how we feel, or how we anticipate we'll feel. Damasio (1994) has shown that the feedback emotions provide is required to make even simple cognitive decisions, like which clothes to wear in the morning.

In order to understand and describe how emotional states can be connected or chained to elicit behaviour that is beneficial to the user, several practical questions must be addressed.

1. How can we tell emotions apart?
2. What emotional states should we be trying to elicit with design?
3. What characteristics of products must be addressed to affect people's emotions?
4. In what sequence should we elicit emotions?

1. How can we tell emotions apart?

The term “emotion” is often used to refer to a number of different states of consciousness and accompanying physiological states. In his research on emotions elicited by the aesthetic properties of products, Desmet (2002 p3) differentiates four types of “affective states”. This term includes (a) Emotions, (b) Moods, (c) Sentiments, and (d) Emotional Personality Traits. The concept of “feeling” is considered to be a part of the conscious experience of the physiological changes brought on by emotions. (Desmet 2002)

Affective states can be differentiated based on how they are described, how they are expressed and by their underlying, physiological dimensions. One model for describing the four affective states has two dimensions; intentional vs. non-intentional and acute (i.e., short), vs. dispositional (i.e., longer lasting) states.

	Intentional	Non-intentional
Acute	Emotions	Moods
Dispositional	Sentiments	Emotional traits

Table 1 - Dimensions of Affective States

(Desmet 2002 p4)

This means that emotions are relatively short (i.e., acute) in duration, but are directed at something in particular (i.e., intentional). Personality or emotional traits display themselves over longer periods of time (i.e., dispositional) and are not directed at anything in particular. (see Table 1).

Another way to differentiate affective states is by their two underlying, physiological dimensions. Everything we experience is either good or bad, or somewhere in between. This is called “value”

and is defined as the range between pleasant and unpleasant. All our experiences are affected, in part, by the “state” of our bodies. This body state helps to determine the intensity of good or bad and is called the level of “arousal” (Cacioppo and Petty 1989). Arousal can be defined as the range between anxiety and boredom. Combining the dimensions of value and arousal gives us eight distinct classes of emotions, with the middle being neutral. (see Figure 1)

Figure 1 - Emotional State Circumplex (van Gorp 2006)
(adapted from Russell 1980 and Desmet 2002)

Emotions are expressed externally through facial expressions, body posture, breathing patterns, vocalizations and behavior, and internally through feelings and changes within the body. Over longer periods of time, an individual who is disposed to express certain emotions is attributed a “personality trait”. Imagining an individual who is often depressed, it is easy to see that there are visual, interactive and behavioural characteristics associated with many personality traits. We also tend to behave in the same way when experiencing particular emotions. For example, *Curiosity* leads to the urge to explore, while *Anger* makes us look similar every time we feel it (Desmet 2002). Emotion changes how we *appear* to others, how we *interact* socially and how we *behave*. How we appear, interact and behave leads others to attribute personality traits to us over time. The human tendency to anthropomorphize means that we also attribute personalities to products and interfaces (Reeves and Nass 1998) based on how they appear, interact and behave.

2. What emotional states should we be trying to elicit with design?

Positive and negative “affect” change how intensely we focus our attention in the world. Positive affect promotes a relaxed body and open, creative thinking. Negative affect promotes a tense body and more detail-oriented thinking. Positive affect is linked with the tendency to approach and negative affect is linked with the tendency to avoid. (Norman 2004) Emotions persuade us to direct our attention to one piece of information over another. The intensity level of the emotion often determines the strength and focus of attention. In evolutionary terms, early humans may have paid more attention to the high-intensity emotions elicited by danger in their environment, thereby improving their chances for survival. (Reeves and Nass 1998)

The Yerkes-Dodson (1908) law describes how arousal (or stress) levels affect performance. As stress levels rise, so does performance. This continues up to a point where optimum performance is reached. After this point, as stress (or arousal) continues to rise, performance declines. From this law, we can see that some stress or anxiety is good for performance, but too much stress damages performance. (see Figure 2)

Figure 2: Yerkes-Dodson Law (van Gorp 2006)
(adapted from Yerkes-Dodson 1908)

The focus of attention determines what enters our consciousness and what doesn't. Attention is required to make other mental events happen, like thinking, remembering and making decisions. Attention also selects the information considered relevant from the vast quantity of information

that is available to our senses. The contents of consciousness therefore correspond quite closely to our subjective experience of reality. Our senses communicate to us what is going on both outside our bodies and within them, while consciousness reflects those changes in information selectively. (Csikszentmihalyi 1990) When an individual's attention becomes focused by a challenge that she knows she can handle with her existing skills, a great sense of enjoyment is experienced, along with peak performance, Csikszentmihalyi (1990) calls this phenomenological state "flow". Flow is characterized by shifts in time perception as well as increases in both skills and self-confidence. (Csikszentmihalyi 1990) Achieving and maintaining flow requires balancing the arousal dimension of emotion. (see Figure 3)

Figure 3: Anxiety, Boredom and Flow

(Csikszentmihalyi 1990 – Dots, arrows labels added: van Gorp 2006)

Flow appears at the boundary between boredom and anxiety. As we increase the challenges we face, we become more anxious. Re-entering flow involves increasing our skills to match these challenges. As we increase our skills, we become bored. Here, re-entering flow involves increasing the challenge to match the increased skills. (Csikszentmihalyi 1990)

The dimensions of the affect circumplex are Pleasant vs. Unpleasant, and Anxiety vs. Boredom. This last dimension is the same as that shown in the preceding figure. Both the Yerkes-Dodson law and Csikszentmihalyi's ideas of flow describe how a balance of stress or arousal leads to a state of optimum performance and increased skills. Transferring the notion of flow to the affect circumplex, we can draw the flow area in approximately the same place as in Csikszentmihalyi's diagram, in the middle of anxiety and boredom. (see Figure 4)

Figure 4: Emotional States w/Flow Area (van Gorp 2006)

Circumplex adapted from Desmet 2002, Russell 1980)

Flow (adapted from Csikszentmihalyi 1990)

Negative, “unpleasant” stimuli tend to evoke stronger cognitive, emotional and physiological responses than positive stimuli. (Cacioppo et al 2004) In other words, negative stimuli arouse more attention. The flow area has been placed toward the positive side of the circumplex, since negative things will demand more attention and therefore break the flow more easily. Csikszentmihalyi (1990) has found that flow can appear in both positive and negative circumstances, and is more dependent on arousal levels than value. In most cases however, the designer should be attempting to elicit positive emotional responses. Flow is a good goal in terms of eliciting emotions for work or task-oriented behaviour. However, it cannot be assumed to be the most appropriate state for every context.

3. What characteristics of products must be addressed to affect people’s emotions?

Reeves and Nass (1998) have found that people respond to products and interfaces in the same way they respond to other people. We attribute personality to products and judge them based on how they *appear*, how they *interact* with us and how they *behave*, just like people. We anthropomorphically judge whether their personality is *dominant* or *submissive* when compared to similar products and then compare that personality to our own. Users choose products, in part, based on how similar they feel to the perceived personality of the product. (Jordan 1997 as cited in Jordan 2000) (Fogg 2003) For an emotion to become a personality trait, it is consistently expressed over a long period of time. A personality trait has effects on how an individual

appears, interacts and behaves. Interactive products, which also have an appearance, manner of interacting and mode of behaviour, are also attributed a personality and elicit emotional responses. (Reeves and Nass 1998)

When we use interactive products, input from the user results in feedback from the interface that constitutes a dialogue or conversation. Because of this “conversation”, the attribution of personality is easier than with a less interactive product. The form of the feedback also plays a part in personality attribution. Comparing the two lines of text below, the meaning conveyed by the text is altered by the perceived personality of the typeface. (see Figure 5) This is especially true when the content of the message is somewhat ambiguous in its emotional tone. (Isen 1999)

What do YOU want??

what do you want?

Figure 5: Personality and Meaning (van Gorp 2006)

Some visually descriptive words for the first text block might be dark, big, heavy, angular, rough and masculine. Some descriptive words for the second text block, when compared to the first, might be lighter, smaller, lighter in weight, rounded, smoother and more feminine. Although the content is the same, the meaning each block of text conveys is different. Either one might appeal to you, depending on what type of personality you have, and what state you’re in at the moment. Dominance and submissiveness are relative. While the top text block may be dominant in appearance in this context, it may be judged as submissive when compared to a different font. Extending this example to visual characteristics that convey personality, we can associate simple personality types with very similar sets of words. Expressing more complex and nuanced personality types tends to require combinations of visual, interactive and behavioural characteristics.

Visually, a **Dominant Personality** is:

darker, bigger, heavier, angular, rougher and more masculine than a...

Submissive Personality, which is...

lighter, smaller, lighter in weight, rounded, smoother and more feminine.

www.sitesdesignedbysites.com

www1.folha.uol.com.br

Figure 6: Wrestler, Alpha Male Monty Brown and Barbie
(comp: van Gorp 2006)

Because men can embody characteristics considered feminine in some cultures, and women can embody characteristics sometimes considered masculine, this is not an issue of gender. Rather, it's an issue of what visual and interactive characteristics have been associated with particular personality traits over millions of years of evolution. (Reeves and Nass 1998) Users seek people and products that they feel have personalities similar to their own (Fogg 2003) or who they aspire to be.

Perceptions of personality are also elicited via dialogical or social interaction. In an interface or product, this can take the form of information architecture, navigation structure, sounds and visual cues. Like visual characteristics, the emotional meaning of a social exchange depends not only on the content of the interaction (e.g., the words that are said) but also on the form of that content (e.g., *how* those words are said). Kemper (1978) has described social interactions in terms of two dimensions; power vs. punishment and high status vs. low status. The relationship

between power and status can also be illustrated with a circumplex. This circumplex corresponds to the circumplex of emotional states and allows us to visualize the effects of power and status shifts on value and arousal. An interface can offer power and status to a user by being easy to interact with, polite, and by offering the user power in the form of options and control. (see Figure 7)

Figure 7 - Interaction and Emotion Circumplexes (van Gorp 2006)
(adapted from Kemper 1978, Russell 1980 and Desmet 2002)

The appearance and interaction of a product or person projects a personality. Personality can also be visualized in terms of two dimensions: dominance vs. submissiveness and friendliness vs. hostility. The personality of a product or interface is judged for similarity against the user's own personality and state. (see Figure 8)

Figure 8 - Personality and Emotion Circumplexes (van Gorp 2006)

(adapted from Plutchik and Conte 1997, Russell 1980 and Desmet 2002)

Finally, the perception of personality may lead to behaviour. If a personality is perceived as similar, behaviour may result in the form of approach. A personality that is perceived as dissimilar may result in avoidance. The arousal level of the user will determine the level of motivation to do either. An interface might motivate a user by offering rewards, for example. (see Figure 9)

Figure 9 – Behaviour and Emotion Circumplexes (van Gorp 2006)

(adapted from Russell 1980 and Desmet 2002)

4. In what sequence should we elicit emotions?

The human tendency to attribute personality to objects and interfaces means that we are always judging and comparing. By addressing the three issues of *appearance*, *interaction* and *behaviour* for interfaces in the same way we would for people, we can establish rapport and trust between people and the products they use.

Changing the attitudes, goals, or behaviour of others in a voluntary way involves persuasion. One way to see persuasion is as a chain of emotional states that affect the way information is processed before, during, and after the information is encountered. (Saari et al 2004) State chaining is an idea derived from Neuro-Linguistic Programming and Learning Theory. It involves directing the elicitation of a chain of related emotional states in a way that moves the person towards more ideal information processing and beneficial behaviours. The chains consist of emotions, rather than longer-lasting affective states like moods or sentiments.

The states in a chain should have behaviours associated with them that are beneficial to the user within the context. *Curiosity*, for example, usually leads to exploratory behaviour. When learning to use a new product or interface, eliciting a state of *Determination* might help a user to persevere when attempting to solve a problem. In state chaining, a problem state is connected with a desired end state by utilizing transition states in between that help to bridge the gap in value or arousal levels. (Dilts and De Lozier 2000a)

If a user has a negative experience, and experiences frustration, they may quit using the product that elicited that emotion. Chaining them from their problem state (i.e., frustration) to a more desirable state involves moving them through related transition states. In the diagram below, the states are related by value. In this case, the values are:

- something *negative*,
- to something *somewhat negative*
- to something *somewhat positive*
- to something *positive*

Figure 10: State Chaining: Problem, Transition and Desired States (van Gorp 2006)
(adapted from Dilts and De Lozier 2000a)

The affect circumplex displays the underlying relationships between emotions. Pieter Desmet (2002) has developed a circumplex that lists sixty-nine emotions relevant to the experience of products. However, Desmet’s circumplex does not rank the emotions by their levels of value and arousal, but merely assigns them to a particular octant of the circumplex.

Desmet also focused on emotions elicited mainly through aesthetics or appearance, rather than interaction and usage. For the purpose of illustrating the notion of state chaining, interaction emotions derived from Thoits (2004) have been added by the author to Desmet’s sixty-nine emotions. These social emotions include *shame*, *guilt*, *pride*, *embarrassment*, *fear*, and *frustration*. Further studies would need to include a more formal approach for determining a complete set of emotions elicited by interaction and their relative ranks within the circumplex.

The emotions were then ranked by the author according to their levels of arousal and value. This ranking was based on a survey of definitions of the emotion words. The expanded circumplex (see Figure 11) functions as a “map” of the emotional landscape. Like nearby towns on a conventional map, the relative proximity of emotional states makes some emotional transitions more likely and comfortable to experience than others.

By ranking the emotions in terms of value and arousal, it is easier to see the relationships and relative similarities between emotional states. The proximity of particular states to one another allows the designer to plan chains of emotional states that can help users recover from errors, enhance skills, gain self-confidence and experience more pleasure with products.

Figure 11: The Affect Circumplex (van Gorp 2006)
(Emotions adapted from Thoits 2004 and Desmet 2002)

An example of a possible emotional state chain (see Figure 12)

- An inexperienced user is feeling a little *NERVOUS* about using her new computer.
- After starting up the computer, she sees a brightly coloured “Internet’ button.
- The bright colour of the button is pleasant and peaks her *curiosity*.
- *CURIOUS* about what the button will do, she clicks it and the computer sets up her Internet connection.
- Within minutes, she is surfing the Internet and checking the score from the previous evening’s world cup match.
- After finding the score, she is *EXCITED* as she appraises that the computer is a convenient way to accomplish her goal (i.e., to see if her team has won).

- Reflecting as she shuts down the machine, she is *PLEASANTLY SURPRISED* at how easy the computer was to operate

From being *NERVOUS*, the user has moved through several states to become *PLEASANTLY SURPRISED*, an emotion within the flow area. (see Figure 12) (van Gorp 2006)

Figure 12: Emotional State Chain into Flow Area (van Gorp 2006)

(Emotions adapted from Thoits 2004 and Desmet 2002)

(Flow adapted from Csikszentmihalyi 1990)

State Chaining helps to explain why some emotions are more likely to occur during interaction than others. It also helps the designer visualize how emotions are elicited during every step in a product interaction. This knowledge serves to educate the intuition of designers and illustrate the process for other stakeholders. Combined with the skills of the experienced designer, flow, state chaining and the emotion map are tools that allow for a practical understanding of what emotions

to elicit, how to elicit them, and in what sequence.

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